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First long length industrial High Temperature Superconductor

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ABSTRACT

In ARIES is foreseen to produce and characterize HTS tapes of REBCO of higher performance with respect to the one developed in EuCARD2. We aim to develop the process to deposit REBCO film on a 50 μm substrate of stainless steel, a novel process never attempted so far. The scope of ARIES program is to increase the world record of engineering critical current density, J_E , obtained in EuCARD2, from 400-600 A/mm^2 at 4.2 K 20 T to 600-1000 A/mm^2 . This Deliverable report describes the successful delivery of various long lengths, fulfilling the ARIES goal of obtaining more than 100 meters of length with engineering critical current density above 800 A/mm^2 .

ARIES Consortium, 2019

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For more information on ARIES, its partners and contributors please see <http://aries.web.cern.ch>

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Delivery Slip

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Executive summary

The system developed for EuCARD2 has been reviewed and adapted to manufacture HTS (High Temperature Superconductor) coated conductor depositing REBCO (Rare-Earth Barium Copper Oxide) on a 50 μm thick substrate, half the previous thickness of 100 μm . The use of such thin stainless steel tape is an absolute novelty in the panorama of coated conductor.

Bruker HTS GmbH (BHTS) has adapted the equipment and the process and has obtained tapes with record current density, well beyond the ARIES goal, see report MS45. However, a subtle unexpected issue consisting in a bi-directional bending (bi-stable effect) has adversely affected the process. The process has been adjusted to mitigate this effect with the consequence of reducing the critical current of 30%, still fulfilling the goal of ARIES ($> 100\text{ m}$ with $> 800\text{ A/mm}^2$ at 4.2K, 18 T).

The program has been anticipated and not only the first long length of material has been produced, as requested by the initial ARIES program and by this deliverable D14.4, but actually all the long length have been produced and are under delivery from BHTS to CERN. In total 413 m of HTS tape of 12 mm width and 50 μm substrate thickness have been produced.

1. Introduction

The scope of the task 5 inside the WP14 of ARIES is to develop a new process for the deposition of a HTS layer with 1-2 μm thickness onto a substrate of stainless steel of only 50 μm thickness.

The previous work of EuCARD2 WP10 (Future Magnets) had the main goal of developing a high performance deposition process of REBCO onto a more traditional 100 μm thick stainless steel. Indeed world record critical current densities, at 4.2 K and high field of 20 T – the relevant area of interest of high field magnets for accelerator (and fusion), were obtained in EuCARD2. When calculated over the only superconductor cross section, i.e the REBCO layer, the critical current density $J_L = I_c/A_{\text{REBCO}}$ was almost a factor two above the –other –best industrial producer, SuperPower in the USA. However, the gain in terms of engineering critical current density, $J_E = I_c/A_{\text{tape}}$, was more modest: still the world record but just above the main competitor (all other companies are rather far). This is because BHTS, the EuCARD2 and ARIES Industrial partner for HTS, has developed deposition technology using stainless steel tapes, rather than Hastelloy as all other manufacturers. The thickness of stainless steel tape is 100 μm , vs. a thickness of 50 μm currently employed for Hastelloy, thus reducing the resulting engineering current density of stainless steel substrate with respect to Hastelloy substrate, for a given J_L .

The primary goal of ARIES has been set to increase J_E by factor of 1.5-2 with respect to EuCARD2 by developing the technology for 50 μm substrate of stainless steel. Then a second step will be to industrialize the process for long length ($> 25\text{ m}$) to be used for conductor for demonstrator of high field magnets.

2. Deposition technology and special equipment

2.1 DESCRIPTION OF THE PROCESS

The process of producing coated conductor via plasma laser deposition (PLD) can be summarized in the following main steps.

1. Preparation of stainless steel tape substrate (with surface smoothness at few nm level). Any defect in this phase is assumed as a potential reason for a fatal defect of conductor performance.
2. Deposition of thick film of ceramic buffer layer for texturing made of Ytria-stabilized zirconia (YSZ), via ABAD (alternating ion beam assisted deposition) at ambient temperature. ABAD is a proprietary process of BHTS. The YSZ is about $2-3 \mu m$ thick.
3. Deposition of REBCO (RE= yttrium in our case) by PLD technology, a process carried out at high temperature. BHTS utilises Yttrium as rare earth. The YBCO film is about $2 \mu m$ thick.
4. Coating with a few μm of silver to protect the superconducting layer (typically $1 \mu m$ on the backside and $2-4 \mu m$ on the functional side (YBCO side).
5. Coating with $2 \times 20 \mu m$ (or other thickness) of copper for final stabilization.
6. The resulting tape is shown in Fig. 1. Of course our process involves heavily the step 1. Dealing with a thinner tape, with much less strength is not easy and the handling necessitate an improving of the tooling and of the brushing system.

However, the novel property of the stainless steel tape strongly affects all process since its mechanical strength became more comparable with the one of the other layers. In particular the vacuum coating step 2 and step 3 which is carried out at high temperature, required new set up and a modification of the process, as described below. Step 4 and 5 are less affected by the thickness of the substrate even if, also in this case, new handling system have to be set up to cope with the reduced mechanical strength of the tape.

2.2 PREPARATION OF THE SUBSTRATE

Polishing of the 50 μm thin substrate tape was performed via abrasive based processing employing a drum technology which was successfully used for 100 μm thick tape manufacturing for the EuCARD2 project. Polishing procedure had to be re-adjusted taking in to account twice lower tension force which is allowed to apply to twice thinner tape. Also all steps of tape handling (tape rinsing, quality inspection of the surface, etc.) were revised in order to reduce tape tensile force.

2.3 THE PLD-300 DEPOSITION EQUIPMENT

The PLD process is by far the most critical for the final performance, since it concerns the deposition of the superconductor itself. For this process has been set up a new machine, by BHTS, jointly owned by BHTS and CERN, called PLD-300. The PLD-300 equipment has been set up in 2017 just on time for ARIES and has been used for the test and R&D for ARIES. In Fig. 2 is shown a picture of the PLD-300 at the first production for ARIES in presence of the CERN and BHTS teams.

For successful deposition of YBCO layer onto thin substrate a re-adjustment of heating regime is needed to suppress fluctuations of tape temperature. Main reason for that is twice lower heat capacity of the 50 μm thick tape in comparison with “standard”, 100 μm thick substrate. During deposition, when the substrate is moving together with the guiding drum through the deposition window, heat losses caused by IR emission lead to twice higher deviation of temperature in 50 μm thick tapes. To compensate this effect a new optimum in quasi-equilibrium substrate heating had to be found. Nevertheless, already at first deposition run with not optimized conditions, the critical current was high enough to reach record values for engineering current density. This means that the new setting of PLD process may be not very far from the “standard” conditions used in the past. Anyhow such optimization being one of the tasks of the given project, it may take some time.

Fig. 2. Picture of BHTS and CERN teams in front of the new pilot PLD line PLD-300, installed in the BHTS premises and capable of coating tape lengths of almost 100 m with 12 mm wide tape and almost 300 m with 4 mm wide tape. Alzenau, De, 17 January 2018.

3. Results

3.1 PROBLEM OF BI-DIRECTIONAL BENDING (TAPE BOW SHAPE) AND SOLUTION

HTS tapes coated on the 50 μm substrate reveal a strong tape curvature (tape bow) due to intrinsic film stresses of the coatings. By its nature, the intrinsic film stress is a structure and microstructure sensitive property. Compressive stresses arise if the film expands parallel to the surface. Typically, the compressive *intrinsic stress* is a consequence of the high film density caused by higher energy of the condensing and bombarding atoms and molecules. On a macroscopic scale the bow of a coated substrate is the result of intrinsic and extrinsic film stresses and strongly depends on the film thickness and the substrate thickness (Stoney equation). Therefore, with the stainless steel tape only being 50 μm thick, a much higher tape bow is observed after ABAD and PLD coating. By bending, the 50 μm thick tape exhibits a transient area between transversal to longitudinal curvatures. This leads to a characteristic “knee” when the free tape is bent e.g. by own weight. Within this knee, curvature does not exceed the critical one: no deterioration of I_c is observed after flattening¹, see Fig. 3.

This effect, though not of great influence on critical current after flattening, as said before, can be detrimental for tape manipulation during cabling and winding. Indeed the tension remains and the accuracy of mechanical position for tape cutting (meandering formation during Roebel cable formation) is certainly more difficult. In addition the thickness of the Roebel cable may also be increased by residual bending (bow shape) of the tape, thus decreasing the effective current density and then the magnetic efficiency. Therefore BHTS has worked hard to find a solution: by modifying the deposition cycle, the bow in the transverse direction of the tape has been seriously reduced, see left picture of Fig. 3.

¹ E. Kebabze, S.D. Guest, S. Pellegrino, Bistable prestressed shell structures, International Journal of Solids and Structures 41 (2004) 2801-2820

3.2 METHOD TO CURE THE BI-DIRECTIONAL BENDING

As said above, the bending of the tape is mainly due to intrinsic stress in buffer layer and the structural mismatch between the ceramic layers and the stainless steel. The process optimized at BHTS for the 12 mm tape is described in section 2.1, and the two process involving ceramic deposition at high temperature are responsible of the tape bow. Especially the rather thick ceramic YSZ layer (2-3 μm , approximately 5 to 10 times thicker than the IBAD process used by other manufacturer) is causing the bow. The measures taken by BHTS to mitigate the bow has been to deposit the YSZ buffer layer also on the back. The modified ABAD process is schematically illustrated in Fig. 4.

The modified process can yield very good results but, once longer length units have been tried it showed to be not fully reliable when made with a reduced number of iteration steps. In general it was found a reduction of 30% in current capability with respect to the exceptional high value obtained in the short sample reported in MS45. This is caused because the tape is flat at the end of the ABAD process with backside coating; however, the YSZ layers that were deposited when the tape was not flat, during the process (see first step of iteration 2 of Fig. 4), are not anymore well aligned once the tape is flattened by backside deposition (see last step of iteration 2 in Fig. 4). Especially in the portion of the tape near the edge the buffer the layer is mis-oriented and this results in reduction of the effectiveness of the PLD process.

Taking all precautions, a total sum of 413 m of conductor has been manufactured. The Cu coating has been tailored to obtain a good $J_{\text{engineering}}$ on all, with a mix of standard $2 \times 20 \mu\text{m}$ Cu thickness, and $2 \times 5 \mu\text{m}$ Cu thickness. The best unit #17703, originally 25 m long, has been used for deep characterisation and has been subdivided in multiple shorter units. In particular the 8 m long unit (17703-1-2-0) has been coated with $7 \mu\text{m}$ Cu coating as test of “reduced Cu coated thickness”. The positive result has allowed to decide for the very low Cu content of the unit coated with only $5 \mu\text{m}$ thick copper. Three unit lengths, all of the last batch #17707, have rather low critical current.

However, thanks to the thin 50 μm stainless steel substrate and the much reduced Cu deposition thickness, $2 \times 5 \mu\text{m}$, its J_{eng} is well above 400 A/mm² at 4.2 K 18 T, i.e. the value of the previous EuCARD2 target and still an appreciable value in the panorama of the world suppliers.

In Fig. 5 is reported a table with all tape identifications and their properties. Please note that all tapes have been measured at 5 T, 4.2 K, and the value at 18 T and 20 T is scaled according to the well verified power law $I = I_0 \times (B/B_0)^{-\alpha}$. In our case we have used $\alpha=0.75$, following the measurement of the first sample, see report MS45.

			$I_c(B=5T)$	$I_c(B=18T)$	$I_c(B=20T)$	$J_e(B=18T)$	$J_e(B=20T)$
<i>Tape ID</i>	<i>Length(m)</i>	<i>Cu layer (μm)</i>	<i>measured</i>	<i>scaled</i>	<i>scaled</i>	<i>calculated</i>	<i>calculated</i>
15088-1-1-1	27	2x20	1,564	598	553	499	461
15088-1-2-1	30	2x20	1,888	722	668	602	556
15088-1-2-2	27	2x20	1,888	722	668	602	556
17702-1-1-0	79	2x20	1,621	620	573	517	478
17703-1-1-1	1	2x20	3,386	1,296	1,197	1,080	998
17703-1-1-2	1	2x20	2,707	1,036	957	863	798
17703-1-2-0	8	2x7	2,063	789	729	889	821
17703-1-3-0	15	2x20	2,105	805	744	671	620
17705-1-1-0	75	2x5	1,866	714	660	850	785
17706-1-1-0	75	2x5	2,330	892	824	1,061	980
17707-1-1-1	24	2x5	1,025	392	362	467	432
17707-1-1-2	26	2x5	1,090	417	385	497	459
17707-2-1-0	25	2x5	902	345	319	411	380

Fig. 5. The 413 m of tape produced with a 50 μm stainless steel substrate and carried out till final stage (Cu coating) by BHTS for the ARIES 2 in the frame of WP14, task 5.

It has to be noted that much more than one long unit length has been produced, as was required by the delivery plan. Actually, **all ten unit lengths with $L \geq 25$ m have been already manufactured and qualified** with critical current measurements, though at 5 T.

Out of the total length of 413 m, 160 m (#17703-05-06) present a current density above, or much above, the target of this Deliverable that was set at 800 A/mm² at 18 T, 4.2 K.

Some 72 m (# 17702) are above 600 A/mm² and, as above mentioned, the 75 m of #17707 are of lower grade but still acceptable as high current tapes.

The #17703 (except subunit 17703-1-3-0), #177056 and #17706 have current exceeding 800 A/mm² and in certain cases above the record value of 1000 A/mm² at 18 T, 4.2 K, near the best value of MS45.

However one can note that considering the 1 km material initial processed by the company the yield of the 50 µm thick substrate of stainless steel is pretty low. Most material is lost during the mechanical polishing, however all important step have low yield.

3.3 LESSON LEARNT AND FEEDBACK TO MANUFACTURING PROCESS.

Dealing with 50 µm thickness of stainless steel tape proved to be harder than expected. The tape is prone to damage very easily and the softening of the stainless steel at the high temperature of ceramic deposition is an issue. The bow is difficult to eliminate. All these issues have become very important or were raising when reducing the thickness from 100 to 50 µm. For example the influence of temperature fluctuation is deemed to be much larger for the 50 µm than for the 100 µm. After a deep analysis and discussion we concluded that:

- 1- A possible solution to reduce the 20-40% I_c-performance loss during back side coating is to modify further the buffer deposition process, by alternating or parallel coating of functional side and back side. However, this would require a significant effort, also economical, not possible in the frame of the ARIES limited frame.
- 2- Possible measures to reduce the technical issue (handling, mechanical stability, sensitivity to spring on drum technology, etc..) are:
 - a. Using substrate with a higher strength (e.g. Hastelloy)
 - b. Replacing mechanical polishing by electro-polishing,
 - c. Avoiding spring-supports on drum technology,
 - d. Improving tape handling set-up of the equipment used.
 - e. Again, all above measures, required a deep revision of the process and of the handling chain, not possible inside the ARIES program.

Referring to the result of the analysis presented above, it has been decided to swiftly produce all the possible lengths of the 50 µm production, to verify its usefulness, or not, in magnet technology.

4. Conclusions and future plans

The goal of the D14.4 deliverable has been fully achieved and actually exceeded, with all production of ten long lengths foreseen in the ARIES program fulfilled.

Now we will proceed to fully characterization as required by the MS46 “Characterization of first long length conductor”, due by M36 (30 April 2020).

As a further step we will test this tape to verify its use in magnet technology: suitability for winding, adaptability to solder (especially low Cu coating thickness), etc...

5. List of abbreviations

ABAD	Alternating Ion Beam Assisted Deposition
HTS	High Temperature Superconductor
PLD	Plasma Laser Deposition
REBCO	Rare Earth Barium Copper Oxide
YBCO	Yttrium Barium Copper Oxide
YSZ	Yttria-Stabilized Zirconia